

Comprehensive Risk Assessment of Health, Safety, and Environmental Hazards at the Municipal Solid Waste Landfill in Batna City

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ABSTRACT

Health, Safety, and Environmental (HSE) hazards present significant challenges across various sectors, impacting individuals, organizations, and the environment. The hazards in question are linked to health risks, safety concerns, and environmental effects. In landfill operations present significant challenges that can adversely affect workers, nearby communities, and the environment. Addressing these HSE hazards requires comprehensive risk assessments, implementation of effective control measures, regular monitoring, and adherence to regulatory standards to ensure the safety of workers, protect public health, and minimize environmental impact. Inadequate waste management practices in Batna landfill, such as improper covering of waste materials, poor maintenance of sorting facilities, and lack of emission monitoring, often lead to significant health, safety, and environmental issues. Conducting a comprehensive risk assessment for landfill operations in Batna City, involves a systematic approach to identify, evaluate, and mitigate potential health, safety, and environmental (HSE) hazards. This study investigates occupational health and safety (HSE) protocols at a municipal solid waste (MSW) landfill in Batna City, with a primary focus on high-hazard zones: the incinerator, sorting facility, and locker. The Sistema Ambiente serves as our risk assessment tool, enabling us to evaluate potential hazards affecting workers and the environment and subsequently implement corrective measures to limit the severity of their impacts. Research indicates substantial health concerns for employees, encompassing biological, physical, and ergonomic hazards, across all three sectors. Environmental risks are primarily associated with air pollution from biogas emissions and the burning of medical waste, as well as soil contamination from leachates. These findings highlight the need for well-planned risk management strategies to safeguard both worker well-being and the environment at the Batna landfill.

Keywords: Waste management, Landfill, risks, health, safety, environment, Sistema ambiente tool.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increase in both population and economic growth directly influences the escalation of waste production. Forecasts suggest that the generation of global municipal solid waste will rise from 2.01 billion tons in 2016 to an estimated 3.40 billion tons by 2050 [1].

Countries, irrespective of their development stage, face the challenge of managing growing volumes of waste, a trend that closely aligns with increases in both population and income [2]. The method of treatment adopted for municipal solid waste (MSW) in Algeria is landfilling, mainly due to its simplicity and low cost. The financial costs of waste management also vary with the disposal method. Waste collection and uncontrolled landfilling generate substantial financial costs, most of which derive from collection and transportation [2]. Therefore, landfills, as sites of biochemical waste degradation, are known to release hazardous gases, dust, and leachate, posing significant risks to both environmental integrity and worker health [3].

Over the last few decades, numerous studies on the topic of the "triangle of death" have examined the possible health impacts of illegal waste disposal, but their findings have been inconsistent. Certain authors determined that the elevated cancer mortality rate in the region is associated with pollution stemming from poor waste management practices and illegal disposal. The pollution can reach different levels of the environment and, consequently, affect the public health in different ways[4]. Other researchers downplay the considerable effect of improper waste management on public health [[5], [6], [7], [8]]. Therefore, this research intends to contribute in this area.

Knowing that for landfills, effective management of waste is essential and encompasses the processes of collection, transportation, and treatment. It also emphasizes health and safety measures to protect workers and reduce the costs associated with workplace accidents and diseases [9]. The International Labor Organization (ILO) reports that annually, over 2.3 million workers succumb to occupational accidents or work-related diseases. The ILO emphasizes that preventing these illnesses and accidents should be a paramount concern for all workplace participants, noting that the global economic cost of these incidents reaches approximately \$3 trillion each year. According to the National Social Security Fund for Salaried Workers(Caisse Nationale des Assurances Sociales des Travailleurs Salariés, CNAS), Algeria recorded 42,032 occupational accidents reported in 2021 (on all insured employees). The number of daily allowances paid by the social security fund exceeded 2 million (Algerian Dinar), while expenditure on occupational accidents and illnesses exceeded 26 million dinars (193000 \$). The catastrophic impact on employees and their families cannot be completely measured; nevertheless, the ILO has assessed the significant financial

strain of failing to invest in Occupational Safety and Health to avert workplace accidents and diseases.

In Algeria, numerous laws aim to prevent workplace hazards by enhancing understanding, developing accident prevention strategies, reducing costs, and fostering a safety-aware culture among employees and employers. Health, Safety, and Environment (HSE) adopts a comprehensive strategy that integrates practices, policies, and protocols to safeguard employees, contractors, visitors, and the environment at work sites. This strategy emphasizes risk evaluation, fostering a culture of safety, and compliance with relevant regulations and industry norms, underlining the role of international standards in directing these activities.

A significant obstacle confronting a site such as the landfill in Batna, which only adheres to Algerian laws and regulations, lies in implementing these laws and guidelines, primarily due to gaps in legislative instruction and a lack of a health, safety, and environmental (HSE) culture among staff. Notwithstanding this, a review of the literature reveals that occupational health and safety concerns for personnel engaged in landfilling activities have received insufficient attention [10]. The present study aims to evaluate environmental pollution and health effects on employees associated with waste landfilling utilizing Sistema Ambiente, a software designed to assess health, safety, and environmental quality. These standards form a solid foundation for ISO 9001, ISO 14001, EMAS, OHSAS 18001 and ISO 45001.

2. PUBLIC HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT RISKS RELATED TO LANDFILLS

The accumulation of waste has become a real urban problem, causing serious impacts on public health and environmental integrity. Currently, landfill as an appropriate technological option for municipal solid waste (MSW) disposal is used especially with small costs and simple operation [11]. However, this solution can cause environmental concerns (mainly related to waste biodegradation) and public health. Landfills accumulate waste in specialized cells, sealed daily with soil or synthetic materials, which over time can lead to soil and groundwater contamination and the release of strong odors, posing significant environmental and social challenges [12], [13], [14]. Activities such as methane management and electricity production at these sites also present considerable risks [15], [16], [17], [18]. It was determined that landfills could potentially release gases into the atmosphere, such as CO₂, H₂S, CH₄, and NO_x. These gases are linked to respiratory health issues and certain specific cancers, such as lung cancer. Carcinogenic risks were discovered to differ among studies, primarily due to the differing traits of the landfill. Various studies indicate that the

environmental contamination caused by landfills poses increased dangers to children residing near those sites [19]. According to Lombardi (2023), Table 1 presents an overview of Lindfill’s impact on the environment and public health [20] . Another high-risk activity is the use of heavy plant and machinery and its interaction with people and the landfill environment. Environmental health concerns encompass more than just a collection of anxieties regarding radiological health, water and wastewater management, air pollution control, solid waste disposal, and occupational health; they also pose a risk to future generations [21].

Table 1: Effects of waste dumpsites on public health and environment

Landfill Emissions	Main Hazards	Effects on Public Health and Environment
Landfill gas	CO ₂ CH ₄ NO _x SO _x H ₂ S	Nausea, headaches, vomiting, coordination loss, and elevated blood pressure. Exposure to high levels of methane (CH ₄) can cause coma and fatalities from asphyxiation. Increased risk of respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. Neurological impairments and deficits, alongside vascular issues and further respiratory conditions; risks from extreme flammability and unpleasant odors.
Dust, Particulate matter	Heavy metals	Carcinogenic
Leachate	Chemicals (e.g., heavy metals, acids and microorganisms	Soil, surface, groundwater contamination, affecting food supplies.
Uncovered solid waste	Sharps; pathogens, flammable waste; geotechnical instability	Waste slides; open burning; illness; injuries; alterations in biodiversity

(Source: Lombardi et al., 2023)

3. PRESENTATION OF THE LANDFILL OF BATNA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

The Batna landfill is located in the El Biar area, near the commune of Oued Chaabat and the quarries. It covers an area of 25 hectares. It is situated in the southwest, 9 km away from the city of Batna. Its topography is flat land and its geology is rocky soils with a clayey tendency. Hydrologically, there are no wadis close to the site, except for the Chaabat River (Figure 1).

Fig (1): A satellite image of Batna's landfill

In Batna city, as in many other cities in developing nations, inadequate solid waste management has been reported. Municipal waste is collected, weighed, and subsequently transported to a locker, where it is compressed and deposited in a landfill (Figure 2). Occasionally, some of these waste materials will be separated and sold for recycling. A thermal treatment incinerator has been set up in the landfill to manage the healthcare waste produced by the medical facilities in Batna city.

Fig (2): Landfill of Batna city

Composition of household waste in Batna city is shown in Table 2. This waste analysis indicates that the organic component constitutes the most significant portion by wet weight, averaging 55% in Batna. Textiles and plastics succeed this portion.

Table 2: Composition household waste in Batna city [22]

Fraction		Household Waste in Batna city (%)
Organic Matter		56.84
Plastics	PET	1.41
	HDPE	0.67
	Others	8.82
Paper / Cardboard	Paper	15.03
	Cardboard	2.72
Metals		1.22
Textiles	Sanitary textile	7.88
	Other	2.30
Glass		1.81
Others	Hazardous waste	0.12
	Others	0.18
Total		100 %

Bio-waste stored in the locker releases water more or less quickly. These juices, mixed with rainwater leaching from the surface of the traps are called leachate. They concentrate toxins and contaminants, particularly heavy metals, in mixed trash. Water and soil resources are at risk due to leachate. Batna landfill began operations in 2007, before the first trap was covered or protected, so leachate enters directly into the ground and can reach a groundwater table, polluting the water resource. In 2023, a second locker was created but this time it is protected by a geomembrane but not in a safe way (as seen on the locker photo). Additionally, even if the membrane is well installed, there is no synthetic material with infinite life; pollution is simply moved in time. To reduce the risk, any sanitary landfills that are filled or converted for gardening are consistently monitored for many years [19].

Leachate spills loaded with pollutants and toxic substances can therefore occur in the environment around the landfill site, endangering plants, animals that ingest them and, at the top of the food chain, humans. Humans are more directly affected when the landfill is located near a water table supplying drinking water to the population. The decomposition of bio-waste landfilled also produces biogas, primarily consisting of methane, a potent greenhouse gas, along with toxic substances (like heavy metals) that pollute soil and groundwater. Xu et al. (2018) carried out research to determine the relationship between air pollutants linked to landfills and the respiratory health of children residing near a specific landfill in China [23]. It was reported that CH₄, H₂S, CO₂, NH₄, and various other air pollutants were emitted during the anaerobic decomposition of waste in the MSW landfills.

Batna's landfill has recruited ragpickers to sift through certain materials in the locker. These operators encounter multiple pollutants emitted from the breakdown of bio-waste. The personnel at the sorting facility and the incinerator face numerous hazards. According to Limoli et al. (2019) landfills can lead to the release of harmful gases, dust, and leachate into the environment as a result of biochemical waste decomposition, potentially causing significant effects on both the environment and public health [24], [25], [26], [27].

A Health, Safety, and Environment (HSE) plan defines the strategies for meeting specific health, safety, and environmental objectives [28]. Strict protocols must be followed during work operations at major hazard sites in order to reduce the possibility of serious incidents that could have a negative influence to the environment, the public, and employees [29], [30], [31]. The HSE management system at the landfill of Batna is organized into distinct processes to enhance the visibility of its various elements.

Compliance With Laws And Regulations

The HSE procedures adhere to two main international standards:

- _ ISO 45001 for health and safety management.
- _ ISO 14001 for environmental management.

In Algeria, one of the pillars of an HSE management system’s foundation is the current legal and administrative regulatory landscape. This requires collaboration with the appropriate ministries and the labour inspectorate to meet and prioritize all necessary regulations for the Batna landfill. These requirements will be monitored closely and full compliance will be ensured. Regarding environment and safety, the following two texts are implemented on the site in compliance with legal and administrative regulations:

- Law No. 03-10: environmental protection within the framework of sustainable development.
- Executive Decree No. 02-427: pertaining to the guidelines controlling worker education, awareness, and training in the area of preventing occupational hazards.

Ensuring workplace health and safety is a legal, ethical, and crucial activity that significantly enhances both individual and organizational performance; thus, risk assessments are essential for the effective implementation of health and safety protocols.

3.1. Management Roles and Responsibilities

Based on the requirements identified, the HSE policy and objectives have been clearly defined by management and brought to the attention of the landfill’s staff at all organizational and management levels allocate the necessary resources for the exercise of this HSE policy, which is approved by management and posted in the appropriate places (Figure 3).

Fig (3): Landfill Center of Batna organization chart

3.2. HSE Organizational Structure

To effectively implement the HSE policy and achieve its goals across all divisions, section heads and site managers are appointed as HSE representatives for their respective areas. HSE structure of the Landfill of Batna is as follows (Figure 4).

Source: Authors

Fig (4): Operational organization chart of the HSE management system

The Locker, Sorting Center, and Incinerator at the Batna Landfill are identified as the highest risk areas.

3.3. Management Responsibilities

The General Manager, with support from the Deputy General Manager and the Health and Safety Commission, is responsible for developing and managing the HSE Management System. A designated HSE Management Committee is established to :

- Develop a comprehensive Health, Safety, and Environment (HSE) policy tailored to the technical requirements of the landfill.
- Allocate adequate resources and support to implement the HSE policy effectively across the organization.
- Define and communicate annual objectives, action plans and corresponding performance indicators.
- The HSE commission responsible for the application of Ministerial Instructions.
- Evaluate adverse events and implement necessary corrective measures.

3.4. Preservation of Safety and Protection of the Environment

Protective strategies are established to reduce the likelihood and impact of risks. The policy at the Landfill center incorporates employee safety and environmental conservation by:

- The medical care that employees receive when signing their contract with the company.
- Providing the best Personal Protection Equipment (PPE) that is available in the Algerian market.
- Raising awareness about the potential risks from company operations.
- Ensuring proper disposal techniques for special waste.

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS

4.1. Risk Assessment

Risk assessment involves identifying hazards, evaluating their potential impact, and determining their likelihood and severity to effectively manage and mitigate risks. This process is structured in three phases: initially, a list of potential hazards in the target process is compiled to identify risks; this is followed by a risk analysis to deepen understanding of these risks; finally, the potential impacts of these risks are assessed, using qualitative and quantitative methods or a combination of both [32]. Finally, the decision-making step occurs, during which the decision is taken to decrease or accept risks.

To ensure workplace safety and environmental protection in Batna landfill, we will assess the risks encountered by employees and the ecosystem throughout different workplaces (Sorting center, Landfill locker and Incinerator). We began our inquiry in the administrative division by interviewing the managers. Following that, we examined the operational sector, where we questioned employees and staff. Furthermore, we closely inspected various facilities and equipment. All collected data has been analyzed using a program called Sistema Ambiente, where we assessed risks and reviewed the different elements of the HSE policy applied at the Landfill. Consequently, by employing the Sistema Ambiente software, every risk associated with a particular work phase is extensively evaluated to ascertain its possible impact.

4.2. Sistema Ambiente Software

The "Sistema Ambiente" software by Iride simplifies the management and organization of occupational health, safety, and environmental information within companies (Figure 5). Compliant with European and American standards, and tested in all industrial and service sectors, it provides a standard basis for risk management: analysis, prevention, employee protection and management of environmental parameters. We evaluate the risks inherent in

company activities and their interrelations by reconstructing a comprehensive view of the work organization, considering not only emerging anomalies but the entire operational reality. Individual worker profiles are created and managed, encompassing aspects such as working hours, training, workplace risks, Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), and accident and incident records. To conduct the analysis, the system provides questionnaires that can be used to gather the most in-depth but above all real data.

Source: Home page

Fig (5): Sistema Ambiente software home page

4.3. Implementation

The checklist serves as a key method for risk assessment. Developed typically from experiences, either through previous risk assessments or from historical failures, checklists catalogue potential hazards, risks, or control lapses. These procedures are used to identify hazards, assess risks, and evaluate the effectiveness of existing safety measures. HSE standards recommend a five-step risk assessment process, complete with a detailed checklist to ensure thorough evaluations:

- Step 1: Identifying hazards
- Step 2: Identifying the Population at Risk
- Step 3: Evaluating the risk and adequacy of current controls
- Step 4: Recording significant findings
- Step 5: Risk assessment review.
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5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents and discusses the findings of the implementation of Sistema Ambiente software to assess the HSE in the Landfill of Batna.

5.1. Hazard's identification

The following hazards are discernible for the three workplaces.

▪ **Workplace : Incinerator**

After looking over the incinerator and performing a task analysis, we found that the workers face the following risks:

Concerning employee health and safety:

- Exposure to intense heat in a contained workspace might result in radiation burns.
- Injuries brought on by sharp objects: potential for penetration or cuts to the skin as a result of ineffective PPE worn at work.
- Toxin exposure resulting from skin contact, either direct or indirect, with medical waste.
- Extended communication Long-term exposure to ashes and fumes can cause major health problems.

Concerning Environment:

The solid residues from incineration are bottom ash (which is the solid residue recovered from the base of the combustion furnace. They contain heavy metals and organic pollutants (dioxins)) and ash. Atmospheric emissions are essentially carbon dioxide.

▪ **Workplace: Landfill locker**

We identified the following hazards after looking into the crammed landfill locker, getting feedback from staff members, and case studies:

Concerning employee health and safety:

- Cuts from sharp items (blades, metal, glass, etc.);
- Heatstroke, a medical disease resulting from the body overheating, usually from prolonged exposure to high temperatures or physical activity in such settings;
- Back pain caused by improper posture at work.

For the Environment:

- Risk of locker explosion from biogas (methane) accumulation.
- Fire hazard due to the combustible nature of the waste.
- It should be mentioned that two fires that started in the first locker affected the landfill of Batna, which by 2023 will have processed more than 100 million kg of waste. This incident led to the spread of unpleasant odors to the Batna landfill, causing discomfort especially in the urban area of Hamla;
- There is a risk of underground water contamination due to the insufficient design of the landfill's leachate drainage system;
- Collisions and dust spread due to the unpaved road and lack of warning signs.

▪ **Workplace: Sorting center:**

In the Sorting center, we have a list of risks that employees may encounter:

- Dragging, crushing, or tangling may result from rotating components or pinch points;
- Fire and electric shock risks;
- Accidents involving sharp objects;
- Unmeasured noise levels that could eventually have a negative impact on health;
- Pedestrian-engine collision.

5.2. Population at risk

The table below determines the population exposed to hazards in the landfill of Batna.

Table (3): Population at risk in the landfill of Batna

Workplace	Incinerator	Landfill Locker	Sorting center
Population	-Employees of the incinerator -People close to the working area	-Lone workers	-Sorting employees -Waste stocking employees
How	-Direct contact with medical waste -Indirect exposition to infected air.	-Associated risks with the type of work	-Associated risks with the type of work

Source: Authors

5.3. Evaluating the risk and adequacy of current controls

A risk assessment involves a detailed examination of the workplace to determine hazards, risks, currents controls and adequacy of controls (Table 4). Once the risks are identified, we must allocate a risk rating. The decision on whether it is sufficiently safe to continue with the task or if further control measures are necessary to reduce or remove, the risk will rely on the rating. As we lack any accident or illness data in Landfill, we can conduct a Qualitative Risk Rating, which primarily helps us assess if the risk level is minimal, low, medium, or high. This summarized form of risk evaluation is commonly used to determine which hazard should be given precedence over others in terms of deciding what to do and when.

Table (4): Assessment of risk and adequacy of current controls

Workplace	Hazards	Risks	Level of risks	Current Controls	Adequacy of Controls
	Solid waste: cutting objects,	Biologic and injuries	High	PPE	Inefficient

Incinerator (Healthcare waste)	bacteria and pathogens in healthcare waste	risks for employees			
	Toxic gases after treatment	Chemical risk for employees and environment	High	PPE Filters	
Landfill Locker (Household waste)	Solid waste: heavy metals, leachate, bacteria and pathogens	Biologic risk, chemical risk	High	None	None
	Working posture for sorting	Ergonomic risk	High		
	Flammable waste	Fire risk	High		
Sorting Center (Household waste)	Solid waste: cutting objects, bacteria, pathogens and	-Biologic and injuries risks -Respiratory risk -Noise risk	High	PPE	Inefficient
	Working posture for sorting	Ergonomic	Moderate	Electricity Safety System for sorting	

The results approve the adverse health effects reported in the literature as:

- Physical risks: contusions, falls, cuts, musculoskeletal disorders (MSD) linked to handling, repetitive and rapid movements, vibrations, etc.
- Biological risks: contamination through skin wounds and stings due to exposure to microorganisms, inhalation of dust and infectious or allergenic agents.
- Chemical risks: skin contact with corrosive, irritant, toxic, carcinogenic products, etc., treatments that may generate exposure to gases and dusts.

- Noise risks associated with sorting machines: vibrating tables, conveyors, screens, compressors, balers, motors for sorting line feeding, etc.

5.4. Recording significant findings

With the use of Software Sistema Ambiente, we are able to classify all of the data that has been collected through the area of study and organize it into the relevant columns. We therefore recorded our findings using the software

5.5. Risk assessment review

Risk assessments are dynamic documents and should not merely be stored away. They must be evaluated frequently to confirm that they continue to be precise and current. The effectiveness of this risk evaluation and ultimately the creation of a long-term, sustainable, and efficient HSE management system is significantly reliant on the involvement of the responsible individuals at the Batna landfill and the continuous monitoring of risks.

6. CONCLUSION

The assessment of risks (ergonomic, chemical, psychological, biological, and physical) in Batna Landfill has revealed that the current safety conditions are deemed unacceptable risk and necessitate immediate and substantial modifications. The conducted analysis has revealed that the primary risks are associated with the environment (Biogas and leachate) and the employees of the locker and incinerator (exposed to cutting objects, bacteria and pathogens in healthcare waste, smoke and gas from biogas and incinerator) emphasizing the importance of offering workers specific information and training on these matters. These effects and accidents were related to mismanagement, unawareness, lack of safety culture and other factors; the effectiveness of any HSE management system depends on the commitment of managers to the policy. Moreover, financial constraints are the primary barrier to adopting safety measures and embracing innovative concepts.

Therefore, we recommended the following actions:

- Give employees appropriate PPE;
- Adjust work schedules in the event of severe weather;
- Build welfare structures with restrooms, showers, medicine cabinets, and changing areas;
- Arrange for routine maintenance for all of the landfill's machinery and facilities, including the vehicles, sorting machine, and incineration filter;
- Start research on the duration of exposure to specific activities (such as noise exposure or incinerator use);

- Implement a new HSE management system based on ISO standards (14001 and 18001) to enhance workplace safety and safeguard the environment without causing trouble for the law or obstructing work or activity flow.

Nonetheless, these results should be considered preliminary research. Since additional studies are required to address more efficiently the identified risk profiles, integrating them with targeted preventive and protective strategies. All pertinent parties, including managers, safety experts, and employees, should work together. This will make it easier to guarantee that their work environments are secure and that their staff are protected against risks.

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Author contributions

SL, TO and RS: investigation, methodology, software and writing.

Competing interests

The authors have declared that no competing interests.

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